

INFLUENCE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP RISK-BEARING AND BUSINESS PLANNING ON TECHNOPRENEURIAL INTENTION OF BUILDING TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION STUDENTS IN COLLEGES OF EDUCATION IN NORTH-EAST, NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14997252>

ABSTRACT

The study examined the influence of Entrepreneurship risk-bearing and business planning on Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology students in colleges of Education in North-East, Nigeria. Two specific objectives and two null hypotheses guided the study. A descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The population of the study was 203 respondents and total population sample was used. Questionnaire titled SEETIQ was the instrument for data collection, and was validated by three experts from ATBU Bauchi and Federal College of Education (T) Potiskum. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach alpha, and reliability coefficient of 0.7 was obtained. Six research assistants helped in the data collection. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS), Version 26 was employed for data analysis. Linear regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that risk-bearing and business planning had significant influence on Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Students in Colleges of Education in North East, Nigeria. The study recommends that National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) should implement specialized training programme focusing on risk bearing in business and business planning strategies for Building Technology students so as to enhance their Technopreneurial Intention in North-East Nigeria.

Keywords: Risk-Bearing, Business Planning, Technopreneurial Intention

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship education is viewed as a learning process whose objective is to influence attitudes, behaviour, values and intentions towards being self-employed. Entrepreneurship education includes all activities aiming to foster entrepreneurial mindsets, and covering a range of aspects such as idea generation, start-up, growth, business idea generation, risk bearing, marketing strategies in business, business plan, venture management in business, attitude toward entrepreneurship and innovation (Jones, *et al.*, 2022). Entrepreneurship education is being considered as an avenue for educating students for developing creativity, innovative and technopreneurial intention. The European Commission, for example, reports that the primary purpose of entrepreneurship education is to promote entrepreneurial attitudes, develop entrepreneurial intention and influence mindsets of potential entrepreneurs (Bałandynowicz-*et al.*, 2023). Technopreneurial

intention refers to the intention of an individual to decide to be an entrepreneur by scanning the environment, identify opportunities to take advantage of, marshal resources, and put the ideas into action by establishing their own ventures. Technopreneurial intention is the cognitive state of mind prior to executing a behaviour or initiating action (Barba-Sánchez, *et al.*, 2022).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Despite the objective of entrepreneurship education to curtail the growing unemployment issue by inculcating knowledge, skills and values as well as a means of enhancing technopreneurial intention of its recipients, still this entrepreneurship education received by the technical education graduates of colleges of education seems not to be harnessed (Peschl, 2021). Researchers such as Peschl, *et al.* (2021); Chernenko, *et al.* (2021); Salhieh and Al-Abdallat (2022) submitted that recipients of entrepreneurship education suffered in aspect of business fund management, business idea generation, risk bearing in business, developing interest in business start-up, business plan, market competition and positive attitude towards becoming entrepreneur. Likewise, Chernenko, *et al.* (2021) posited that fund management is one of the problems encountered by entrepreneurs when they conceive the ideas of starting their own enterprises. Similarly, Ncube & Matlala, (2024), asserted that the problems students have in entrepreneurship education course is in business idea generation, risk bearing in business, and business plan writing. It is against this background that the researcher intends to determine the influence of entrepreneurship education on technopreneurial intention of building technology students in colleges of education in North-east, Nigeria.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of this study was to determine the influence of entrepreneurship risk-bearing and business planning on Technopreneurial intention of Building Technology students in colleges of education in north-east, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. Examine the influence of risk bearing in business on Technopreneurial intention of Building Technology Education students in Colleges of Education in North-east, Nigeria.
- ii. Determine the influence of business plan on Technopreneurial intention of Building Technology Education students in Colleges of Education in North-east, Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Based on the research objectives, the following research questions guided the study:

- i. What is the influence of risk bearing in business on Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Education students in Colleges of Education in North-east, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the influence of business plan on Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Education students in Colleges of Education in North-east, Nigeria?

HYPOTHESES

The following null Hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance in the study;

- H₀₁** Risk bearing in business has no significant influence on Technopreneurial intention of Building Technology Education students in Colleges of Education in North-east, Nigeria.

H₀₂: Business plan has no significant influence on Technopreneurial intention of Building Technology Education students in Colleges of Education in North-east, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneurship and the Nigerian Economy

Nigeria is the most heavily populated nation in Africa, which is naturally blessed with millions of acres of arable land, thirty-eight billion barrels of state oil reserves, large gas reserves, an assortment of unused and untapped mineral resources, and a wealth of manpower and human capital by reason of its estimated population of above 160 million people. However, as stated in a study by Kohler and Bowra, (2020), Nigeria still falls far short of both the economic and social advancement required to positively impact and influence the welfare and wellbeing of the average Nigerian. It is imperative to state that a document by the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (2019) posited that entrepreneurship has the proclivity to power up the Nigerian economy, and statistics show that there are at present over 17 million business enterprises employing over 31 million Nigerians. In the same vein, Mbagwu (2018), argued that entrepreneurship accounts for over eighty percent (80%) of business enterprises employing an estimate of 75 % of the total workforce in Nigeria.

The Role of an Entrepreneur in Economic Development

Verver, *et al.* (2019) stated that out of the three existing classes of classifications in society namely; entrepreneurial class, land owners, and workers, the entrepreneurial class is considered the main class and the vital economic performer. Lounsbury, *et al.* (2019) posited that entrepreneurs are individuals who through creative organization of resources, produce novel innovation or improve on existing ones. Zvavahera, *et al.* (2018) described an entrepreneur as a major player in the economy, and a vehicle for economic transformation, revitalisation and development. Lombardi, *et al.* (2020) contended that by combining diverse factors or aspects of production in the production process, entrepreneurs are able to identify or recognize entrepreneurial opportunities and accept the outcomes of their actions, based on the risks involved. This is consistent with other theories on entrepreneurship that associate the role of an entrepreneur with risk taking; particularly in seemingly uncertain circumstances and economic down turn (Etemad, 2020). Therefore, it can be asserted that the role of an entrepreneur is associated with innovation and the ability to fill market gaps by closing the short-falls between market demand and supply which serves as a catalyst for economic development (Korankye-Sakyi, 2019).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design: A descriptive survey design was used for this study. Descriptive survey design is considered relevant in obtaining the opinion of the respondents on the Influence of Entrepreneurship Risk-bearing and Business Planning on Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Students in Colleges of Education in North-East, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design aims at accurately and systematically describing a population, phenomenon or situation and provides answers to what, when, where and how one variable affects the other. Descriptive survey research design was appropriate in this study because it helps to describe the influence of business risk bearing and business planning on the technopreneurial intention of Building Technology Education students in colleges of education.

Area of the Study: The study was carried out in the North-East Nigeria, which is made up of six states. The states are Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba and Yobe. The North East Nigeria was created on the 27th May, 1967, while on the 3rd February, 1976 the old North East region was divided into Bauchi, Borno and Gongola states. Further division took

place in 1991, when Gongola state was divided into two states as Adamawa and Taraba states. Likewise, during the same period, Yobe state was created out of Borno state. While Gombe state was created out of Bauchi state on the 1st October, 1996.

Population of the Study: The population of the study comprised 203 NCE II and NCE III students 2022/2023 academic session that were offering building technology education in the colleges of education in the study area. The reason for choosing NCE II and NCE III students is that the students have been exposed to various entrepreneurship courses and building technology education courses at their level. The distribution of the population is presented in Table 1:

Table 1: Population Distribution of Building Technology Education Students

S/N	Colleges	State	Number of NCE II Students	Number of NCE III Students	Total Number of students
1	Federal College of Education (Technical), Gombe	Gombe	30	26	56
2	Federal College of Education (Technical), Potiskum	Yobe	22	19	41
3	Federal College of Education (Technical), Yola	Adamawa	18	7	25
4	College of Education, Azare	Bauchi	11	7	18
5	Zing College of Education, Zing	Taraba	28	10	38
6	Sir Kashim College of Education, Maiduguri	Borno	19	6	25
Total			128	75	203

Source: Field study, 2024

Sample and Sampling Technique: This study employed total population sample because the population was manageable. This is as a result of the relatively small size of the population, which was 203 respondents. Hence, census sampling technique was used for this study, because Census sampling technique is the statistical enumeration where all the members of the population are studied.

Instrument for Data Collection: Students Entrepreneurship Education and Technopreneurial Intention Questionnaire (SEETIQ) was used as the instrument for data collection for the study. The instrument had three constructs: Technopreneurial intention, Risk Bearing in Business and Business Plan. Each construct of the instrument had ten items, and entailed two sections, namely section A and section B. Section A provided the respondents with the required information on how the instrument should be answered. While section B was designed for eliciting the responses of the respondents based on the research questions in the study. The overall objective of the instrument was to elicit responses of the respondents on the influence of Entrepreneurship Risk Bearing in Business and Business Planning on Technopreneurial Intention of students in Colleges of Education in North-East Nigeria. The items in the questionnaire instrument were measured on a five points Likert’s scale as Strongly Agree (SA) =5; Agree (A) =4; Undecided (U)=3; Disagree (D) =2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) =1.

Validation of the Instrument: The instrument for data collection was subjected to face and content validation by experts in entrepreneurship education, building technology education and measurement and evaluation, from Abubakar Tafawa Balewa

University, Bauchi, Bauchi state and Federal College of Education (Technical), Potiskum, Yobe state. Comments and suggestions of the validates in terms of the appropriateness, wordings, clarity, spellings and grammar were incorporated in producing the final copy of the instrument.

Reliability of the Instrument: Reliability of the instrument was obtained by conducting pilot testing of the instrument outside the study area. In an attempt to measure reliability of the research instrument, the questionnaire was subjected to a pilot test by distributing 30 copies of the instrument to the federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi, which was outside the study area, but has the same characteristics with the area of the study. The result of the reliability test of all variables revealed the Cronbach alpha coefficient of Technopreneurial Intention, Risk Bearing in Business and Business plan were rated very good (>.80). Hence, based on the literature argument that the Cronbach alpha coefficients of greater than 0.70, the instrument was considered reliable for this study.

Method of Data Analysis: Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 was used for analyzing the data for the study. The Descriptive Statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation was used to analyze the research questions. Upper and lower limits of real number was used as a basis for decision making. Such as: 0 -1.4 = Strongly Disagree (SD), 1.5 - 2.4 = Disagree (D), 2.5 - 3.4 =Undecided (U), 3.5 - 4.4 = Agree (A) and 4.5 - 5 = Strongly Agree (SA). While the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using simple linear regression. Meanwhile, in taking decision, null hypothesis was accepted where the *p* value was greater than the confidence level of 0.05 and otherwise the null hypothesis was rejected when the *p* value was lower than the confidence level of 0.05.

RESULTS

Research Question One

What is the influence of risk bearing in business on Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Students in Colleges of Education in North-east, Nigeria?

The descriptive statistics in Table 2 indicates the responses of the respondents on all items related to the variable of risk-bearing in business. Specifically, the mean scores range from 3.37 to 3.94, with standard deviations between .017 and .923. The grand mean is 3.71, with a standard deviation of .682. This result suggests that risk-bearing in business management has influence on Technopreneurial intentions of Building Technology Students in Colleges of Education in North-East Nigeria, because the grand mean stood at 3.71, which falls in Agree section under upper and lower limits of real number.

Table 2: Mean and standard deviations of the influence of risk-bearing in business management on Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Students in Colleges of Education in North-east, Nigeria

S/N	Items	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remarks
1	I believe taking calculated risks is essential for business growth and success.	200	3.70	.923	Agree
2	I am comfortable with uncertainty and ambiguity associated with entrepreneurial endeavours.	200	3.87	.867	Agree
3	I view failure as a learning opportunity and a necessary part of the entrepreneurial journey.	200	3.69	.771	Agree
4	I am willing to invest time, resources, and effort into ventures with uncertain outcomes.	200	3.59	.882	Agree
5	I am open to exploring innovative ideas even if they involve a higher degree of risk.	200	3.94	.862	Agree

6	I carefully assess and analyze risks before making business decisions.	200	3.84	.856	Agree
7	I am willing to step out of my comfort zone to pursue potentially rewarding business opportunities.	200	3.76	.907	Agree
8	I seek advice from mentors or experts to evaluate and mitigate risks associated with business ventures.	200	3.37	.058	Undecided
9	I have a tolerance for failure and setbacks and remain resilient in the face of adversity.	200	3.47	.017	Undecided
10	I embrace uncertainty as a catalyst for innovation and growth in business endeavours.	200	3.83	.677	Agree
Grand Mean			3.71	.682	Agree

Research Question Two

What is the influence of business plan on Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Students in Colleges of Education in North-east, Nigeria?

The descriptive statistics in Table 3 shows the responses of the respondents on all items related to the variable of business plan. Specifically, the mean scores range from 3.23 to 3.92, with standard deviations between .016 and .964. The grand mean is 3.67, with a standard deviation of .688. These results indicate a strong consensus among respondents on the influence of business plan on Technopreneurial intentions of Building Technology Students in Colleges of Education in North-East Nigeria, because the grand mean stood at 3.67, which falls in Agree section under upper and lower limits of real number.

Table 3: Mean and standard deviations of the influence of business plan on Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Students in Colleges of Education in North-east, Nigeria

S/N	Items	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remarks
1	I believe the business plan has strong potential for success.	200	3.77	.751	Agree
2	The business plan demonstrates a clear understanding of the target market.	200	3.76	.720	Agree
3	The proposed business idea is innovative and unique.	200	3.77	.604	Agree
4	The plan outlines a comprehensive strategy for marketing the product/service.	200	3.55	.016	Agree
5	The financial projections provided in the plan are realistic and well-supported.	200	3.73	.777	Agree
6	The plan demonstrates a clear understanding of potential risks and challenges.	200	3.68	.964	Agree
7	The plan includes a well-defined implementation timeline.	200	3.92	.471	Agree
8	The plan effectively outlines the unique value proposition of the business.	200	3.95	.790	Agree
9	The business plan demonstrates an understanding of relevant legal and regulatory considerations.	200	3.35	.854	Undecided
10	The plan effectively addresses potential scalability and growth opportunities.	200	3.23	.929	Undecided
Grand Mean			3.67	.688	Agree

Test of Hypothesis One

Risk bearing in business has no significant influence on Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Students in Colleges of Education in North-east, Nigeria.

The statistical findings in Table 4 reveal a significant influence of risk-bearing in business on the Technopreneurial intentions of Building Technology students in Colleges of Education in North-East, Nigeria. Contrary to the prediction of

Hypothesis 1, this result contradicts the assumption that risk-bearing in business has no significant impact on students' Technopreneurial intentions. This is because p-value obtained (P-value =0.000) is less than 0.05, which is also less than t-value obtained ($\beta = .426$; $t = 9.170$; $p = .000$). This finding implies that the willingness to take risks in business significantly influences the Technopreneurial intentions of Building Technology Students in Colleges of Education in North-East Nigeria. This finding suggests that students who are more comfortable with or prepared for taking business risks are more likely to develop entrepreneurial aspirations in the technology sector.

Table 4: Regression Analysis on the Influence of risk bearing in business on Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Education Students in Colleges of Education in North-East, Nigeria.

Variable	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	p-Value	Decision
Risk Bearing in Business	.426	9.170	.000	Rejected

Test of Hypothesis Two

Business plan has no significant influence on Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Education Students in Colleges of Education in North-East, Nigeria.

The statistical analysis in Table 5 shows a significant influence of business planning on the Technopreneurial intentions of Building Technology Students in Colleges of Education in North-East, Nigeria. As a result, this finding leads to the rejection of Hypothesis 2, which proposed that Business plan has no significant influence on Technopreneurial Intention of students' in Colleges of Education in North-east, Nigeria. Therefore, Hypothesis 2 was conclusively rejected. This is because p-value obtained (P-value =0.000) is less than 0.05, which is also less than t-value obtained ($\beta = .554$; $t = 12.944$; $p = .000$). This finding implies that business planning significantly influences the Technopreneurial intentions of Building Technology Students in Colleges of Education in North-East Nigeria. It suggests that students who engage in or are proficient in creating business plans are more likely to pursue technology-related entrepreneurial ventures.

Table 5: Regression Analysis on the Influence of Business plan on Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Education Students in Colleges of Education in North-East, Nigeria.

Variable	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	p-Value	Decision
Business Plan	.554	12.944	.000	Rejected

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The findings from research question one indicated that risk-bearing in business influences the Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Students in Colleges of Education in North-East Nigeria". This was corroborated by result of hypothesis one, which showed a significant influence of risk-bearing on Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Students in Colleges of Education in North-East Nigeria. Zhang, Wu and Chen (2024) emphasized that the willingness to take calculated risks is a fundamental attribute of successful technopreneurs, as it enables students to explore innovative opportunities and overcome uncertainties inherent in entrepreneurial ventures. Xu (2023) emphasized that students who develop risk-bearing capacities are more likely to initiate and sustain business ventures, as this skill fosters resilience and adaptability in dynamic market conditions. Gahlot (2023) added that risk tolerance, particularly in technical fields like

building technology, promotes creative problem-solving and decision-making, essential for technopreneurial success. Similarly, Pelzer (2018) argued that fostering a mindset that embraces risk-taking helps students transition from theoretical knowledge to practical application, encouraging proactive entrepreneurial behaviour.

However, Chang (2015) offered a contrasting perspective arguing that an excessive focus on risk-bearing might deter students from pursuing entrepreneurial intentions, particularly when they lack adequate support systems or resources to mitigate risks. Chang contended that risk-taking alone, without sufficient preparation and backing, could lead to failures that discourage technopreneurial efforts. This view shows the importance of balancing risk-taking with the provision of mentorship, financial resources, and strategic planning to enhance students' confidence and success in entrepreneurial pursuits. While risk-bearing is a critical driver of technopreneurial intentions, it must be supported by comprehensive educational and institutional frameworks to maximize its effectiveness.

The findings from research question two suggested that the development of a business plan influences the Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Students in Colleges of Education in North-East Nigeria. This was confirmed by test of hypothesis two, which revealed a significant influence of business planning on Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Students in Colleges of Education in North-East Nigeria. Nunden *et al.* (2022) highlighted that creating a business plan provides students with a structured approach to identify and evaluate business opportunities, thereby enhancing their entrepreneurial confidence. Straub *et al.* (2023) noted that the process of business planning helps students develop critical thinking, goal setting, and financial management skills, all of which are essential for technopreneurship. Buhari *et al.* (2024) emphasized that business plans serve as a roadmap, guiding students in strategic decision-making and resource allocation, which increases their readiness to launch and sustain entrepreneurial ventures. Ahmad *et al.* (2024) added that the inclusion of risk analysis and market research in business plans prepares students to navigate challenges and seize opportunities effectively in the dynamic field of technopreneurship.

Conversely, Reina Marín *et al.* (2024) contended that while business plans are valuable, they may not always directly influence entrepreneurial intentions, as students often face barriers such as limited resources and lack of real-world application opportunities. Berbegal-Mirabent *et al.* (2016) further argued that an overemphasis on planning could hinder action-oriented behaviour, particularly for students who may become overwhelmed by the complexities of creating detailed business plans without adequate support. These contrasting views suggest that while business planning is a vital educational tool, its effectiveness depends on the integration of practical experiences, mentorship, and access to resources that enable students to translate plans into action.

CONCLUSION

The study empirically investigated the Influence of Entrepreneurship Risk-Bearing and Business Planning on Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Education Students in Colleges of Education in North East, Nigeria. The study proved that risk-bearing and business planning have significant influence on Technopreneurial Intention of Building Technology Education Students in Colleges of Education in North East, Nigeria. Therefore, understanding and bearing business risks and developing sound business plans are critical components in influencing students' entrepreneurial mindset. By addressing these areas, educators and policymakers can better equip students with the skills and confidence needed to pursue technopreneurial ventures, potentially leading to increased innovation and job creation in North East Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Colleges of Education in North-East Nigeria should include dedicated modules on risk-bearing strategies. The module should cover risk identification, analysis, and mitigation to help students develop the resilience needed to face business challenges and make informed decisions when pursuing entrepreneurial ventures.
- ii. Colleges of Education in North-East Nigeria should ensure that students are taught how to create effective and actionable business plans. Providing resources like business plan templates, case studies, and competitions where students can draft and pitch their plans would encourage them to think strategically about their ventures.

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